

Artistic and Cultural Significance of the Uma Maheswar Image in Singhari (Gadda), Murshidabad

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Abstract

Uma Maheswar cult a part of Shaivism was very popular in Bengal in 10th-12th century CE. Pala kings were very liberal Though they were Buddhists they patronized brahminism along with Buddhism . During the period Buddhist Bajrayan and Brahaminic Tantricism flourished. There were similarities between the philosophy of Bajrajan and that of Hindu Tatntricism. Hindu tantricism aimed at awakening the Kulakundalini which passing through six parts of the body called “satachakraved”, unite with the universal soul (*paramatma*).. In this persuit Purush and Prakriti is very significant. The union of Purush and Prakriti is the prime mover in the path of attaining salvation. Shiva and Shakti is considered as the Tantric Purush and Prakriti. Since Brahaminic tantricism already took its root in eastern India the concept of Uma Maheswar (an intimate positioning of Shiva and Shakti) became very popular in the region. The Uma Maheswar image of Singhari, Murshidabad has been discussed in this line. Singhari has also other significance. It was the capital of feudal king Anadibar Singha founder of Uttar Rarhi ‘Singha’ Kayastha clan of Vatsya Gotra. Anadibar Singha was one of the five Kayasthas invited by legendry king Adisur or Adityasur in last but one decade of ninth century AD. This issue has also been discussed in the article.

Key Words: Uma Maheswar, Tantricism, Ardhanarishwar, Adisur , Anadibar Singha

Introduction

The Uma--Maheswar cult took its root in Bengal during the late Pala period¹ and Sena Period as the stage was set for its embracement due to the already prevalent Tantric cult there, where the union of Purush and Prakriti (Male and Female) was the prime mover in the path of attaining salvation. This tantric cult supposed to be originated from Bajrajani Buddhism which flourished in eastern India, especially Bengal, Odisha and Kamrup. However, some scholars believe that there is evidence of the existence of Brahmanya Tantricism in India, which independently flourished in the Gupta period. From a rock script of 423–24 CE discovered in the village of Gangdharar in central India and issued by Mayurakshak, a minister of a feudal king of the first Kumargupta, significant information is available regarding Tantric worshipping procedures². However, according to Nihar Ranjan Ray, these two streams of Tantricism (Buddhist and Brahmanical) influenced and enriched each other³.

Uma -Maheswar imagery depicts the union of Shiva ad Shakti –Purush and Prakriti of Tantricism. Lord Shiva is considered as Yogacharya in Tantric cult. Shiva as it is said described the procedures of tantric Yoga to awaken Kulakundalini to Parbati (Uma) His consort. And sage Pippalad brought it to human world (Martyo)⁴ Since tantric cult during late Pala period and afterwards spread throughout eastern India (Bengal,Mithila, Odisha and Kamrup) Uma Maheswar image became very popular in the region⁵. The other form of Uma Maheswar image “Ardha-Narishwar”

where Shiva and Parvati is depicted in the same body –in the right side left half of Parvati and in the left side right half is of Shiva though available in Bengal but sporadically⁶.

Iconography of Uma Maheswar (umalingana murti) image as described by N K Bhattashali while discussing about the sculptures of Dacca museum is as follows :

In Shaiva image of this class (Kalyan Sundar image) the god is ordinarily represented sitting on a lotus with the pendant right leg resting on a lotus or on the back of the Bull placed below . His wife Uma sits on His right thigh Her left leg hangs out and is placed similarly on a lotus or on the back of Her vehicle Lion. The god and the goddess are represented as embracing each other. Of all the Shaiva images this variety is the one most commonly met within Bengal”.⁷

The Matsya Puran gives the best and the most detailed directions as to how these images should be made. Hence according to the Puranas, the god may have either two or four hands, He should have a lotus or trident in his right hand and one of his left hands should hold the breast or breasts of the goddess. The goddess embraced should sit on the left thigh of the god and should be gazing at His face. She may be depicted as sportively touching with her right hand the left shoulder of the god, or his right shoulder or his right side. The left hand should hold either a lotus or a mirror. The two maids Jaya and Vijaya, the two sons of the couple –Kartikeya and Ganesha and various other ghosts and supernatural beings are depicted in suitable places.⁸

Historicity of the image

Iconography of Uma Maheswar has been explained In Matsyapurana composed between 4th century BCE to 4th century AD as mentioned above⁹

Uma in the lap of lord Shiva was mentioned in the beginning shloka of Mricchhakatikam- a famous literary piece (drama) by Sudraka in fourth/ fifth century AD. It is referred to there that the lightning like arm of Gauri is placed against the blue neck of Shiva¹⁰.

The Madhai Nagar plate of Lakshman Sena and the Bhawal plate of the same king open with an invocation of lord Shiva, where he is said to have his wife Gauri on his lap like lightning on the autumn cloud.¹¹

It has been mentioned in Sandhyakar Nandi's Ramcharit (twelfth century CE) that Dibyak the Kaibarta warrior who defeated Pala King Mahipal (the-second) and became king of Varendrabhum in 1075 CE and his nephew Bhima were worshippers of Uma Maheswar.¹²

Uma Maheswar of Gadda Singhari , Murshidabad

In the above background, we shall now discuss the Uma Maheswar image found in Singhari village, Murshidabad. Though there are about 10 Uma Maheswar images in the Kandi subdivision

of Murshidabad, the one of Singhari made on black stone is the most beautiful and undamaged. The worship of the image in the village of Singhari holds great historical significance.

Singhari (Gadda Singhari), a village of Burwan P.S, Kandi Subdivision, Murshidabad district West Bengal is a historically significant village having co-ordinates 23.862594(N) / 87.983897(E). Geographically It is located in between two rivers. In the north there is River Mayurakshi and in the south and south-east river Kuye is flowing. Kuye is the same river flows by the side of Shantiniketan, where it is called as Kopai. In regional history this place is very significant. In 882 CE, according to various Kuloshastras and as endorsed by famous scholar Prachya Vidya Maharnab Nagendranath Basu during the period of King Adisur, five Kayasthas and five Brahamins were invited to Bengal from Kanauj for revamping the administration and reorienting the religious practices according to Vedic procedures which the local Brahmans had forgotten by that time due to their intimate association with Buddhism.

Of these five Kayasthas was Anadibar Singh of Vatsya Gotra and Someswar Ghosh of Soukaleen Gotra. Anadibar Singh was offered Singhapur Garh for establishment of his capital. This place is located at 6 miles south west of Kandi-a subdivisional town of Murshidabad and south of Bharatpur. At a distance of ten miles in the east from Singhapurgarh Bhagirathi was flowing. Adityasur(Adisur) offered him 400 villages in the region from Singhapurgarh to Kantaknagar (present day Katwa) which is 17miles south east of Singhapur. This Singhapurgarh or Singhapur is supposed to be present day Singhari (Gadda Singhari). The coordinates mentioned as 23° 53′

(N) and $88^{\circ} 7'$ (E) in the book of Nagendranath Basu are not matching with present day location of the village which is $23^{\circ} 51' 45''$ (N) and $87^{\circ} 59' 2''$ (E). Since the village is located within a valley made of three rivers it shifted its historical location several times due to shifting of river flows.. Consequently coordinates has also changed. However after few hundred years descendants of Anadibar Singh due to intermittent flood caused by three rivers shifted capital to nearby Kandi. In the Kulashastras there is mention of palaces , Vishnu and Shiva temples. Atithishala (guest houses), various large tanks (sarobar) constructed by Anadibar Singha at Singhari but at present except a beautiful black stone image of Hara Parvati (Uma Maheswar) and some broken Vishnu Murtis kept under a very old banyan tree within same premise, nothing is visible. He also established a Lakshmi Narayan Shila as per 'Kulashastra' there which presently is being worshipped as Shridhar Prabhu in a newly constructed temple. Probably all was devoured by the rivers. Even it is difficult to establish the connection of Anadibar Singha and his descendants with the Uma Maheswar figure available in the site. However some scholars finding some south Indian influence in the artistry of the image inferred that Anadibar was originally inhabitant of a kingdom on the bank of Narmada from where he brought it.¹³ But that requires further evidences.

Iconography of the image of Singhari

The image is of about 2-5 ft high and 1.5ft wide. Four armed Maheswar is sitting on lotus. Right leg is hanging and resting on the back of a bull (Nandi). Uma is sitting on left thigh of Shiva. Her left leg is hanging and resting on her vehicle lion. Front right hand of Shiva is touching the chin

of Uma and with the front left hand Shiva from backside of Uma embracing her . In the back right and left hand Shiva is holding lotus and trident respectively. Both heads of Uma and Maheswara are crowned. Crowns are heavily ornamented. Shiva is in Chandrasekhar form here- the half moon is carved on the crown of Maheswara. The combined Uma Maheswar image has been carved in a leaf shaped cave with wavy edge indicating mount Kailas – abode of Lord Shiva. Outside the cave on the top of the sculpture (stela) there are floral and other ornamental motifs. The Stele is pointed upwards

Conclusion

Debate is there regarding the historicity of the image. Scholars pointed out that it is a 10th/ 11th century image of Pala period . In that case it is difficult to relate with Anadibar Singh founder of Sinha Kayastha clan of Uttar Rarh since Anadibar’s time has been fixed as 9th century AD. However from this image and number of other Uma Maheswar images found in the area, it can be inferred that during Pala Period in spite of strong current of Buddhism there was also a stream of Tantricism in Uttar Rarh area of Bengal which was equally strong.

Notes

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6. Ibid P-130
7. Ibid, P-123
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Illustrations

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